

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№5 (3)

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

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*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, may.
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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the expansion of export activities has become an important strategic priority for developing economies, including Uzbekistan. Increasing global competition and rapid digital transformation have created new opportunities for product promotion in foreign markets, highlighting the growing role of modern sales promotion strategies in strengthening international market positions.

Uzbekistan has implemented a number of reforms aimed at enhancing its export potential and improving access to international markets. As a result, the country has achieved significant growth in export volumes and diversification of export destinations. Alongside these positive developments, Uzbek exporters are gradually expanding the use of modern promotion methods to strengthen brand recognition and ensure sustainable positions in foreign markets. Empirical evidence confirms that the effectiveness of export performance is closely associated with the application of innovative marketing practices and strategic promotion tools.

Given these developments, it is important to clearly define the focus of the study. The object of the study is the sales promotion activities of Uzbek exporters in foreign markets. The subject of the study is the effectiveness of modern sales promotion strategies in developing markets.

To better understand this issue, it is necessary to clarify the conceptual basis of sales promotion. In this regard, it should be emphasized that sales promotion is a set of short-term incentive measures aimed at encouraging the purchase or sale of a product or service. Unlike advertising, which creates long-term demand, or public relations (PR), which strengthens corporate image, sales promotion focuses on generating immediate consumer response and achieving measurable results within a short period. International sales promotion, in turn, refers to paid communication initiatives directed at consumers or trade partners that increase the tangible value of a product or brand while involving international stakeholders. In general, sales promotion activities can be classified into price-related and non-price-related promotions, as well as consumer-oriented and business-oriented promotion strategies.

The aim of the research is to analyze the current sales promotion practices of Uzbek exporters and to develop recommendations for improving their effectiveness in developing foreign markets. To achieve this aim, the study sets the following objectives: to examine existing promotion methods, identify development opportunities, and propose strategic solutions based on international experience and modern marketing theory.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Sales promotion has evolved from traditional short-term incentives toward more strategic and integrated marketing approaches. Classical theories emphasize tools such as discounts and trade incentives, while modern research highlights the importance of integrating these tools into broader marketing strategies.

Contemporary research underlines the growing importance of digital marketing in sales promotion activities, particularly in developing markets. The expansion of social media platforms and e-commerce has created new opportunities for firms to interact directly with consumers and promote their products more efficiently. Evidence suggests that digital promotion tools not only reduce marketing costs but also improve targeting accuracy and customer engagement, making them especially valuable for small and medium-sized enterprises operating with limited resources.

Another important concept in modern marketing literature is Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC). This approach focuses on coordinating different promotional tools, such as advertising, sales promotion, and digital communication, into a unified system. Studies indicate that firms adopting IMC strategies achieve higher levels of brand consistency and better overall performance compared to those relying on fragmented promotion methods.

At the same time, research on export marketing confirms that effective sales promotion requires adaptation to specific market conditions, including cultural and economic differences. However, existing studies mainly focus on general models and international companies, while limited attention is given to exporters from transition economies such as Uzbekistan.

Thus, the scientific gap lies in the insufficient analysis of sales promotion strategies used by Uzbek exporters in developing foreign markets. This study differs from previous research by focusing on practical challenges and proposing context-specific recommendations tailored to Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies a qualitative research approach based on the analysis of secondary data, including academic literature, official reports, and publicly available information on export performance.

A descriptive and analytical design is used to examine existing sales promotion practices, assess their effectiveness, and identify key challenges faced by Uzbek exporters. In addition, a comparative analysis with

engagement. International experience confirms that digitalization significantly improves export performance and competitiveness, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises operating in developing markets.

Second, the adoption of a stronger market-oriented approach would enable firms to adapt promotion strategies more effectively to the specific characteristics of target markets, including consumer behavior, cultural preferences, and purchasing power.

Furthermore, greater attention to brand-oriented promotion can contribute to stronger international positioning. Developing recognizable brand identities and emphasizing product quality and uniqueness may reduce dependence on price-based competition while increasing customer loyalty and long-term market value.

In addition, integrating promotion tools within a unified communication framework represents an important opportunity for improving effectiveness. Coordinating digital and traditional communication channels can ensure consistent messaging, strengthen brand recognition, and support continuous interaction with consumers.

Finally, enhancing institutional support mechanisms can play a significant role in accelerating the adoption of modern promotion strategies. Government initiatives aimed at providing training opportunities, market information, and financial support to exporters may further strengthen export capacity, especially in the fields of digital marketing and international market access (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Recommended Integrated Sales Promotion Model for Uzbek Exporters

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effectiveness of sales promotion strategies used by Uzbek exporters in developing foreign markets. The findings demonstrate that traditional promotion methods continue to play an important role in supporting export activities and creating opportunities for further improvement through the adoption of modern marketing approaches.

The research identified several promising directions for strengthening competitiveness, including the expansion of digitalization, improved integration of promotion tools, enhanced brand development, and greater adaptation to target market conditions. The study confirms that the application of modern marketing approaches, such as digital promotion, integrated communication, and market-oriented strategies, can significantly increase export performance and strengthen long-term market positioning. In addition, the enhancement of institutional support mechanisms can further accelerate the successful implementation of these strategies.

Overall, the improvement of sales promotion strategies represents an important factor in enhancing the competitiveness, export potential, and sustainable growth of Uzbek exporters in developing foreign markets.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 5 (3)

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>